

HYDROXYKETONES. PART X. HYDROXYKETONES AND THEIR REDUCTION PRODUCTS AS EFFECTIVE LARVICIDES

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Esters of phenol, isomeric cresols and naphthols with *m*-chlorobenzoic acid have been subjected to the Fries migration and the resulting hydroxyketones reduced to give rise to substituted diphenylmethanes as possible larvicides. Some of these and others, prepared by reduction of the hydroxyketones obtained from the phenolic esters of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid, have been tested and found to be effective against D.D.T.-resistant and susceptible *C. fatigans*.

The present work, which is a continuation of our earlier studies on the mechanism of the Fries migration (Saharia, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, **13B**, 544; Saharia *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1958, **35**, 133 *et seq.*; *J. Vrk. Univ.*, 1958, **2**, 143), deals with the migration of the phenyl, isomeric cresylic and naphthyl esters of *m*-chlorobenzoic acid and subsequent reduction of some of the hydroxyketones.

Phenols as bactericides are known from early times (*cf.* Suter, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, **28**, 269). The halogen atoms and the alkyl groups, when attached to the aromatic nucleus, enhance greatly the bactericidal activity, the positions of these hardly having any appreciable effect. Klarmann *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **44**, 3323; U.S. Pat., 1934, 1,967,825) have investigated the properties of some chloro derivatives of hydroxydiphenylmethane and reported these to be highly potent as bactericides; here again, the positions of the substituents do not greatly matter, though the activity enhances with the size of the alkyl group.

These hydroxydiphenylmethanes were prepared by direct condensation of the appropriate phenol with chlorobenzoyl chloride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Preparation of such compounds is not very convenient and it is often difficult to obtain the chlorobenzoyl chlorides. In contrast to this, the method reported herein is simpler and consists in condensing phenols with *m*-chlorobenzoyl chloride to yield the corresponding esters. These esters on the subsequent Fries transformation at 120° and 160° furnished the *ortho*- and *para*-hydroxyketones which were separated by solubility difference in aqueous sodium carbonate. Reduction of some of the hydroxyketones to the corresponding diphenylmethanes was carried out by Clemmensen's method (Table II). Some of these and others, obtained by reduction of the hydroxyketones isolated on migrating the phenyl esters of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid, were tested as adulticides against house flies (*M. nebulosus*) and as larvicides against mosquitoes (*C. fatigans*), comparative tests being carried out with D.D.T. under identical conditions. As larvicides these were found to be toxic to *C. fatigans* larvæ, though in their effectiveness these did not compare favourably with D.D.T.; the most toxic of these was 4-hydroxy-3'-chlorodiphenylmethane. These compounds were also tested for their toxicity against D.D.T.-resistant *C. fatigans* larvæ and were found to be effective against them, 4-hydroxy-3'-chlorodiphenylmethane having been found the most effective against D.D.T.-resistant larvæ (Table III).

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Esters.—An equimolar mixture of *m*-chlorobenzoyl chloride and phenol was refluxed until the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased; water was added to the cooled product and the separated ester was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution after washing with 2% aqueous

NaOH and water was dried and the ether recovered. The residue was crystallised from ethanol. Analytical data, m.p., crystalline shape and yields of the phenol esters of *m*-chlorobenzoate are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Phenol esters.	Cryst. shape.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
I. Phenyl	Colorless plates	59°	98.4		
II. <i>p</i> -Cresyl	Colorless long needles	79°	85.0	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	68.7	68.1	4.7	4.4
III. <i>m</i> -Cresyl	Colorless leaflets	50-51°	77.6	..	68.4	68.1	4.7	4.4
IV. <i>o</i> -Cresyl	..	54°	73.2	..	68.2	68.1	4.4	4.4
V. α -Naphthyl	Colorless tiny needles	73°	91.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	72.5	72.2	3.7	3.8
VI. β -Naphthyl	Colorless plates	97°	94.6	..	72.0	72.2	4.0	3.8

The *Fries migration of the esters* was carried out, using 1.3 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride and one mole of the ester, in absence of any solvent, at 120° and 160° and the reaction products were worked up in the customary manner.

Hydroxyketones

Phenyl *m*-chlorobenzoate (I) furnished the following two ketones.

(a). *4-Hydroxy-3'-chlorobenzophenone* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 172°. (Found: C, 66.9; H, 3.8. C₁₃H₉O₂Cl requires C, 67.1; H, 3.8%). It did not show any characteristic coloration with ferric chloride. It formed a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 220°.

(b). *2-Hydroxy-3'-chlorobenzophenone* was crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow plates, m.p. 89°. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 3.8. C₁₃H₉O₂Cl requires C, 67.1; H, 3.8%). It developed a deep reddish brown colour with ferric chloride. Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 228°.

The ester (II) afforded only *2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3'-chlorobenzophenone* as yellow hexagonal plates from petroleum ether, m.p. 72°. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 4.7. C₁₄H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 68.1; H, 4.4%). It developed a deep violet colour with FeCl₃. Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 223°.

The ester (III) yielded the following two ketones, which were fractionally separated by their solubility difference in petroleum ether.

(a). *2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-3'-chlorobenzophenone* was crystallised in fine needles from ethanol, m.p. 89°. (Found: C, 68.8; H, 4.7. C₁₄H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 68.1; H, 4.4%). It showed a deep reddish brown colour with FeCl₃. Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 229°.

(b). *2-Methyl-4-hydroxy-3'-chlorobenzophenone*, m.p. 108°. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 4.7. C₁₄H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 68.1; H, 4.4%). It did not show any coloration with ferric chloride. Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone had m.p. 238-39°.

The ester (IV) furnished only *3-methyl-4-hydroxy-3'-chlorobenzophenone* as colorless plates from acetone-alcohol mixture, m.p. 149-50°. (Found: C, 67.8; H, 4.2. C₁₄H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 68.1; H, 4.4%). It did not show any FeCl₃ colour reaction in aqueous medium. Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 237-38°.

The ester (V) yielded only 3'-chlorophenyl-1-hydroxynaphthyl-4-ketone as bright red tiny crystals from benzene-petroleum ether, m.p. 178°. (Found: C, 72.8; H, 3.9. C₁₇H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 72.2; H, 3.8%). Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone had m.p. 181-82° and gave no FeCl₃ colour reaction.

The ester (VI) afforded 3'-chlorophenyl-2-naphthyl-1-ketone as yellow needles from benzene, m.p. 104-105°. (Found: C, 71.9; H, 4.0. C₁₇H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 72.2; H, 3.8%). It developed a deep reddish brown colour with FeCl₃. It did not form any 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

Chlorodiphenylmethanes

Amalgamated zinc (6 g.) contained in a r.b. flask (100 c.c.) was covered with water (1 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 12 c.c.); hydroxyketone (3 g.) was then added and the content refluxed for 24 hours. On cooling, the reaction product was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution was washed and dried and after the recovery of the solvent, the reduced product was purified by distillation. Results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Ketone.	Reduced product.	B.P.	3:5-Dinitrobenzoate m.p.
4-Hydroxy-3'-CB	4-Hydroxy-3'-CDM	184°/10 mm	151°
2-Hydroxy-3'-CB	2-Hydroxy-3'-CDM	182°/9	103-104°
2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-3'-CB	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-3'-CDM	120°/9	154°
2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-3'-CB	2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-3'-CDM	186-87°/9	108-109°
3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-3'-CB	3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-3'-CDM	100°/11	134°

Larvicidal tests of several derivatives of the chlorodiphenylmethane are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Against D.D.T. resistant <i>C. fatigans</i> .			Against susceptible <i>C. fatigans</i> .			
M.L.C. (p.p.m.)	%Mortality.	Conc. (p.p.m.)	Compounds.	Conc. (p.p.m.)	% Mortality.	M.L.C. (p.p.m.)
4.5	95.8	10.0	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-3'-CDM	10.0	98.3	4.3
	57.3	5.0		5.0	54.5	
	5.5	2.0		2.0	9.0	
	98.0	10.0	3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-3'-CDM	10.0	100.0	
	98.3	20.0		20.0	100.0	
10.7	78.4	15.0	2-Hydroxy-3'-CDM	10.0	85.0	3.9
	35.2	10.0		2.5	31.4	
	5.2	5.0	1.25	11.0		
	100.0	10.0	4-Hydroxy-3'-CDM	10.0	100.0	
	96.8	5.0		5.0	99.1	
3.4	63.3	2.5	2-Methyl-4-hydroxy-3'-CDM	1.25	33.0	1.7
	41.6	1.25		20.0	10.0	
	91.2	20.0		15.0	79.6	
	72.5	15.0		10.0	20.2	
	6.2	10.0		5.0	2.5	
15.6	75.9	20.0	4-Hydroxy-2'-CDM	20.0	100.0	9.02
	24.1	15.0		15.0	86.6	
	10.8	10.0	10.0	58.1		
	0.9	5.0	3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-2'-CDM	20.0	100.0	
	100.0	20.0		20.0	99.2	
	95.3	20.0				

TABLE III (cont'd.)

Against D.D.T. resistant <i>C. fatigans</i> .			Compounds.	Against susceptible <i>C. fatigans</i> .		
M.L.C. (p.p.m.)	%Mortality.	Conc. (p.p.m.)		Conc. (p.p.m.)	% Mortality.	M.L.C. (p.p.m.)
	92.6	15.0	2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-2'-CDM	20.0	99.2	
10.3	38.2	10.0		15.0	79.8	9.8
	5.3	5.0		10.0	41.7	
	100.0	20.0	2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-2'-CDM	5.0	19.2	
12.6	95.8	15.0		20.0	99.6	
	66.2	10.0		15.0	83.3	8.9
	6.4	5.0		10.0	67.8	
	63.0	20.0	bis-(p-Chlorophenyl)- trichloroethane (D.D.T. pp.)	5.0	14.2	
				2.5	91.0	
15.0	34.0	10.0		0.5	71.0	0.23
	12.0	2.5	0.1	28.7		

N. B. CB=Chlorobenzophenone, CDM=Chlorodiphenylmethane.

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